

3-Isopropyl-9 α -methyl-1,2,4 α ,9 α -tetrahydroxanthene, Benzyl Benzoates and Chamanen from *Xylopi*a *africana*

E. M. ANAM^a, O. D. EKPA^{*a} and P. V. GARIBOLDI^b

^aChemistry Department, University of Calabar, P. M. B. 1115, Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria

^bDipartimento di Science Chimiche, Università di Camerino, 62032 Camerino (MC), Italy

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Dichloromethane extract of fresh roots of *Xylopi*a *africana* (Annonaceae) gave four compounds, viz. 3-isopropyl-9 α -methyl-1,2,4 α ,9 α -tetrahydroxanthene (1), benzylbenzoate (2), *o*-methoxybenzylbenzoate (3) and chamanen (4). Compound 1 is reported for the first time from natural sources while compounds 2-4 are reported for the first time from *Xylopi*a *africana* (Benth.) Oliver.

The family, Annonaceae is of considerable economic and medicinal importance^{1,2}. It is on this premise that we undertook the investigation of the roots of *X. africana*, a plant extensively exploited in folk medicine in the Cross River State of Nigeria, for medicinal compounds.

Results and Discussion

The structure of compound 1 was determined using mass spectra, ¹H nmr, ¹³C nmr and DEPT. The mass spectrum (EIMS (probe) 70 eV) gave *m/z* (relative intensity) 242.3600 (8) as the molecular ion (calculated for C₁₇H₂₂O : 242.3602). Other important peaks appeared at *m/z* 199 (*M*-43)⁺ (2), 136 (*M*-106)⁺ (20), 131 (*M*-111)⁺ (18), 121 (*M*-121)⁺ (37), 119 (*M*-123)⁺ (18), 108 (*M*-134)⁺ (51), 93 (*M*-149)⁺ (100), 91 (*M*-151)⁺ (35) and 77 (*M*-165)⁺ (34). The peak at *m/z* 199 corresponds to a loss of the isopropyl radical while the rearrangement peaks at *m/z* 136 and 108 represent the fission of the molecule at C₉-C_{9 α} and C_{4 α} -O bonds into two fragments, the first fraction being terpenoid (*m/z* 136) and the second one phenol-methylene (*m/z* 108). The peak at *m/z* 121 is generated by loss of the C₁₃ methyl group from the *m/z* 136 fragment. Cleavage of the C₉-C_{9 α} and C₁₁-O bonds gives a rearrangement peak at *m/z* 91 while similar cleavage at the C₉-C₁₂

and C_{4 α} -O bonds results in the formation of the *m/z* 93 fragment. The presence of the benzene ring is further confirmed by the peak at *m/z* 77.

As can be seen from ¹H nmr spectrum (Table 1) of compound 1, besides the presence of an aromatic ring double bonds, from the calculations of unsaturations obtained from the approximate formula, it is inferred that the compound possesses a tricyclic structure. Examination of the ¹H nmr spectrum reveals also the presence of an *ortho*-disubstituted benzene ring. The multiplet at δ 5.50 can be assigned to a proton of a trisubstituted double bond. A methyl group on a quaternary carbon at δ 1.02 and two methyl groups on a methine carbon at δ 1.02-0.97. The analysis of the ¹H nmr spectrum using bidimensional homonuclear, DQF-COSY correlation permitted a complete map of the coupling scale of all the protons present in the molecule to be traced out in an unambiguous manner.

The ¹³C nmr spectrum of compound 1 (Table 2) shows aromatic signals at δ 116.00-129.00 for the benzene ring, since signals of *sp*² carbon atoms appear at δ 115.00-145.00³. The δ 121.23 signal is assigned to C-12, a trisubstituted carbon, while the low-field shift at δ 152.82 is for the

C-11 (carbon bearing the oxygen). The cyclohexene ring signals appear at δ 23.25 (C-1), 25.27 (C-2) for the sp^3 hybridised carbons and at δ 146.94 (C-3), 119.78 (C-4) for the carbons bearing the double bond³. Besides the arguments already given, the C-13 chemical shifts for the benzene carbon C-5, C-6, C-7, C-8, C-11 and C-12 of compound 1 closely agree with those of equivalent benzene carbons, δ 116.39 (C-3'), 127.12 (C-4'), 119.11 (C-5'), 128.64 (C-6'), 153.77 (C-2') and 121.25 (C-1') of uvarisesquiterpene⁴, a benzylated sesquiterpene. That the substituent at C-3 is isopropyl is indicated by the shifts of δ 34.50 for the methine carbon (C-14), 21.22 and 21.35 for the C-15 and C-16 methyl groups respectively⁵. Comparison of the ^{13}C nmr data to DEPT spectrum and heteronuclear correlation C-H spectrum of the compound allowed for an unambiguous assignments of the ^{13}C resonances. Compound 1 is, therefore, identified as 3-isopropyl-9a-methyl-1,2,4a,9a-tetrahydroxanthene. From bibliographic search, it is confirmed that compound 1 is being reported for the first time from any natural source.

TABLE 1— ^1H Nmr SPECTRUM OF COMPOUND 1

H	Chemical shift	Mult.
6H-15,16	0.97-1.02	dd
3H-13	1.02	s
1H-1	1.50	m
1H-1	1.75	m
2H-2	2.10	m
1H-14	2.20	m
1H-9	2.31*	d
1H-9	2.73*	d
1H-4a	4.30	m
1H-4	5.50	m
4H-Ar-H	6.80-7.10	m

*J 16.2 Hz

Compound 2 : Ir spectrum revealed peaks at 1745 (C=O), 1610 and 1590 cm^{-1} (C=C aromatic ring stretch). Mass spectrum at m/z 212 (M^+) accounts for the formula $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2$ requires 212.2486. Other fragments occurred at m/z 105 (M^+-107) due to ion $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CO}^+$, 91 (M^+-121), $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2^+$ and 77 (M^+-135). The ^1H nmr spectrum of compound 2 gave the following chemical shifts and multiplicities : δ 8.11-8.60 (2H, m, ArH), 7.40-7.60 (8H, m, ArH) and 5.40 (2H, s, Ar- CH_2 -OR). Both compound 2 and the reported¹ benzylbenzoate showed identical ir, mass and ^1H nmr spectral data. Compound 2 found for the first time in *X. africana*, was identified to be benzyl benzoate.

TABLE 2— ^{13}C Nmr SPECTRUM OF COMPOUND 1

Carbon	Chemical shift
C-1	31.30
C-2	23.25
C-3	146.94
C-4	119.78
C-4a	77.85
C-5	116.31
C-6	126.96
C-7	119.85
C-8	129.66
C-9	33.61
C-9a	29.82
C-11	152.82
C-12	121.23
C-13	25.27
C-14	34.50
C-15,16	21.22-21.35

Compound 3 : The ir spectrum of compound 3 showed bands at 1720 (C=O), 1605 and 1590 cm^{-1} (C=C of aromatic ring⁶). Ms at m/z 242.2752 (M^+) corresponds to the formula $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3$, requires 242.2753. Other fractions occurred at m/z 137 (100), 121 (28), 105 (47), 91 (86) and 77 (63). The ^1H nmr spectrum gave the following diagnostic features : δ 8.07-8.12 (2H, m, ArH, ring-B), 7.25-7.59 (5H, m, ArH, ring-A), 6.90-7.00 (2H, m, ArH, ring-B), 5.43 (2H, s, CH_2) and 3.87 (3H, s, OCH_3). The spectral data of compound 3 agreed very closely with

those reported¹ for *o*-methoxybenzyl benzoate. Compound **3** found for the first time in *X. africana*, was identified as *o*-methoxybenzyl benzoate.

Compound 4 : The ir spectrum of compound **4** revealed peaks at 1 690, 1 615 (C=C of aromatic ring⁷). Ms at *m/z* 270.1627 accounted for the formula C₁₈H₂₂O₂, requires 270.1620. Other peaks occurred at *m/z* 255 (69), 164 (59), 149 (100), 107 (99) and 77 (39). The ¹H nmr spectrum gave the following chemical shifts and multiplicities : δ 6.77–7.12 (4H, m, ArH, ring-A), 6.7–6.95 (2H, 2s, H-3,6), 3.91 (2H, s, H-12), 3.81 (3H, s, H-10), 3.25 (1H, septet, H-7), 2.23 (3H, s, CH₃-11) and 1.16 (6H, d, CH₃-8,9). The spectral data of compound **4** were similar to those reported¹ for chamanen. Compound **4**, found also for the first time in *X. africana*, was identified as chamanen.

Experimental

Melting points were determined on a Gallenkamp apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 580B spectrophotometer, EIMS (70 eV) with probe temperature of 200° on a Varian MAT 700 spectrometer, ¹H nmr spectra on a Bruker WH 360 instrument (300 MHz in CDCl₃) using (CH₃)₄Si as internal standard and ¹³C nmr spectra on a Bruker WH 360 instrument (75.43 MHz in CDCl₃) at 200° using (CH₃)₄Si as internal standard. The plant material⁸ was collected from Cross River State, Nigeria in October 1990. Oven-dried roots of *X. africana* were grounded and the coarse powder (500 g) was extracted in a Soxhlet apparatus with dichloromethane for 24 h. Preliminary column chromatography of the concentrated extract (3 g) using silica gel (1.2 kg) and chloroform-methanol (1 : 19) mixture as the eluent gave two fractions : fraction-a (800 mg) and fraction-b (1.5 g), which were mixtures. Fraction-a (800 mg) was chromatographed on a silica gel column (400 g) using EtOAc : n-Hexane (1 : 9) as the eluent. Different eluted fractions were injected sepa-

rately into gas chromatograph for the purpose of identifying which fraction contained a pure product. Contents of test tubes 20–34 (15 mg) contained compound **1** : λ_{max} (CHCl₃) (log ε) 242 (3.17), 277 (3.39) and 285 nm (3.36).

Fraction-b (300 mg) was chromatographed on a silica gel column (120 g) using EtOAc : n-hexane (1 : 9) as the eluent and it yielded compound **2** (35 mg) and compound **3** (35 mg).

Another portion of fraction-b (150 mg) was chromatographed on a silica gel column (60 g) using a mixture of cyclohexane-ethyl acetate (19 : 1) as the eluent. The eluted material, found to be homogenous on tlc, yielded compound **4** (25 mg).

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8. It was authenticated by Dr. D. John, Biological Science Department, University of Calabar. A voucher specimen documenting this collection is deposited in the Herbarium of the University of Calabar, Nigeria.

